

Response of rainfed rice to nitrogen level and postplanting soil management practices

K. K. Katoch, B. R. Sharma, and V. K. Bhatnagar, Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Almora, Uttar Pradesh 263601, India

We studied the response of rainfed rice to 0, 20, 40, and 60 kg N/ha under uncompacted interrow soil (C_0 : 1.36 g/cm³ bulk density) and compacted interrow soil (C : 1.6 g/cm³ bulk density). Soil was a loamy sand with 0.44% organic C and saturated hydraulic conductivity of 45 mm/h. VRS163-2-3 was sown at 23-cm row spacing on 28 Jun 1985 with 18 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Compaction was imposed after complete crop emergence.

Increasing N levels raised yields in general. Compacting soil to a bulk density of 1.6 g/cm³ raised yields by about 15% (see figure). Straw yields did not differ significantly.

Simple linear regression equations (a) $\hat{Y} = 2.19 + 0.014 X$ ($r = 0.98^{**}$) for uncompacted soil and (b) $\hat{Y} = 2.50 + 0.017 X$ ($r = 0.93^{**}$) for compacted soil, correlating rice grain yield and N application, show a higher response under soil compaction. That can be attributed to more water retention and less leaching losses in compacted than in uncompacted soils. □

Grain yield (t/ha)

Yields under varying N levels with and without soil compaction. Almora, India.

Integrated nitrogen management for lowland rice

B. S. Mahapatra, K. C. Sharma, and G. L. Sharma, Agronomy Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital, U. P. 263145, India

An integrated approach or complete substitution of chemical N with bio-organic N sources would help increase lowland rice productivity. We experimented with azolla and *Sesbania aculeata* alone and in combination with chemical N during the 1982-83 and 1983-84 wet seasons.

The loam soil had pH 7.6, 2% organic C, and 0.21% total N. Each treatment received 17 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Zn was sprayed at 60 and 90 d after transplanting.

Yields with *Azolla* incorporation at 45 kg N/ha + 45 kg chemical N/ha, *S. aculeata* as green manure at 60 kg N/ha + *Azolla* inoculation at 30 kg N/ha in 1982-83 and 1983-84, and *Azolla* inoculation at 30 kg N/ha + 30 kg chemical N/ha in 1983-84 equaled yields with prilled urea at 90 kg N/ha (see table). N uptake showed a similar trend.

The lower grain yield in 1983-84 was due to low plant population, dry matter production, and panicle numbers. In 1983-84, low dry matter production resulted in low N uptake.

These results suggest that during the wet season, *S. aculeata* green manuring + *Azolla* inoculation or *Azolla* incorporation or inoculation + chemical N can be substituted for chemical N alone. □

Yield and N uptake with bio-organics alone or in combination with chemical N.^a Pantnagar, India, 1982-83 and 1983-84 wet season.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	
	1982-83	1983-84	1982-83	1983-84
Control	2.7	2.5	47.3	46.3
S 30 kg N + PU 30 kg N	3.4 d	3.0 c	68.2 b	61.9 cd
A 30 kg N + PU 30 kg N	3.5 cd	3.6 ab	70.6 b	71.0 bc
PU 60 kg N	3.3 d	3.0 c	64.0 b	59.0 d
S 45 kg N + PU 45 kg N	4.7 a	3.5 ab	102.5 a	17.8 ab
A 45 kg N + PU 45 kg N	4.6 a	3.7 a	104.9 a	78.8 ab
PU 90 kg N	4.3 ab	3.6 ab	96.3 a	78.5 ab
S 60 kg N + AI 30 kg N	4.7 a	3.6 ab	103.7 a	83.8 a
USG 30 kg N + AI 30 kg N	4.0 abc	3.6 ab	82.3	79.9 ab
PU 30 kg N + AI 30 kg N	3.5 cd	3.5 ab	69.7 b	72.8 b
CD at 5%	0.5	0.6	7.4	10.6

^aValues followed by the same letter do not differ significantly. ^bS = *Sesbania aculeata* green manure, PU = prilled urea, A = *Azolla* incorporation, AI = *Azolla* inoculation at 7 d after transplanting (DT), USG = urea supergranules placed at 10-cm depth at 7 DT.

Slow-release urea fertilizers in sodic soils

D. L. N. Rao and S. K. Ghai, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal 132001, Haryana, India

Volatilization of applied N is high in sodic soils. We are experimenting with timing and N splits to match the plant needs, slow-release fertilizers, deep placement, and urease inhibitors to improve urea efficiency.

In a field experiment in 1984 wet season, we evaluated the efficiency of prilled urea applied all at once (PUW) prilled urea applied in split doses (PUS), one-half at transplanting, one-fourth at 21 d after transplanting (DT) and one-fourth at 42 DT; sulfur-coated urea (SCU), 37.4% N; lac-coated urea (LCU), 30.4% N; and urea 1-g supergranules (USG). All were applied at 120 kg N/ha.

Soil was sodic sandy loam, Calciorthid Natrustalf, pH 8.4, EC

0.37 dS/m, 0.6% organic C, 0.06% total N, and 100 kg KMnO₄ oxidizable N/ha. Plots were 4 × 4 m with 3 replications of 6 treatments in a randomized block design. Jaya seedlings were transplanted at 35 d after seeding. Fields were treated with 10 ppm ZnSO₄ and 5.4 ppm P as single superphosphate. All urea sources except USG were surface mixed followed by flooding to 5 cm. USG was placed 10 cm deep between 4 hills.

Floodwater chemistry (pH, alkalinity, NH₄-N concentration) was monitored at 1330 h daily for 1 wk. Ammonia volatilization was studied separately on bare soil in pots. Semi-open can traps were calibrated in a pure ammonia system. Because the semi-open cans allow a fair exchange of air and water between the outside and the inside of the traps, an artificial microclimate does not develop inside the trap.

SCU did not affect grain yields, LCU decreased yield, and USG increased yield significantly (see table). LCU had no effect on dry matter, SCU and USG increased dry matter. USG significantly enhanced N uptake

Effect of slow-release urea fertilizers on yield and N uptake in a sodic soil. Haryana, India.

N source	Yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)			N uptake efficiency ^a (%)
	Grain	Straw	Total	Grain	Straw	Total	
No N	5.4	3.6	9.0	52	17	69	–
Prilled urea	7.4	5.9	13.2	76	29	105	28
Prilled urea split	7.4	6.2	13.6	84	31	115	35
SCU	7.3	7.4	14.6	86	48	134	50
LCU	6.6	6.4	13.1	71	36	107	29
USG ^b	8.8	8.3	17.1	96	49	145	59
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.5	0.3	0.8	12	11	22	18

^a Apparent N uptake efficiency = $\frac{\text{N uptake in treatment} - \text{N uptake in control}}{\text{N applied}} \times 100$. ^b 1-g granules.

by grains; both SCU and USG enhanced N uptake by straw. SCU and USG significantly increased total N uptake and improved apparent N uptake efficiency.

These results are consistent with floodwater chemistry and ammonia volatilization analyses. SCU and USG were most effective in maintaining low ammoniacal N concentration and alkalinity; PUW, PUS, and LCU were ineffective (see figure). SCU and USG reduced ammonia volatilization losses from prilled urea. Slow-release urea fertilizers like SCU and USG promise to improve fertilizer N efficiency in sodic soils. □

Dynamics of ammoniacal N in floodwater of a sodic soil following 120 kg N/ha applied as PUW or as PUS and slow-release and SCU and LCU. USG were deep placed at 10 cm.

Influence of organic amendments and oils on ammonia volatilization in flooded rice

G. R. Singh and T. A. Singh, Soil Science Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital, U. P. 263145, India

We measured NH₃ volatilization loss from urea with amendments and oils in flooded conditions in a greenhouse study. Soil was Beni silty clay loam, Aquic Hapludoll with 7.2 pH, 1.5% organic C, 24 meq/ 100 g of soil CEC, 24% free CaCO₃, and percolation rate of 14 mm/d. Pots were filled with 16 kg soil amended with 50 ppm of p-benzoquinone (PBQ) and catechol (Cate) and 50 g plant residue babul *Acacia arabica*, khair *Acacia catechue*, and inknut *Terminalia chebula*.

Jaya rice was transplanted at 23 d after seeding at 4 seedlings/ pot. At 5 d after transplanting, coated or uncoated urea was broadcast and incorporated and 1-g urea supergranules (USG) were deep placed 5 cm at the center of 4 hills. Treatments were replicated

twice. A cylindrical frame covered with a heavy-duty polythene bag was immediately placed on each pot and sealed. A petri dish filled with standard H₂SO₄ hung inside the frame. The petri dish was emptied every 4 d, the contents distilled for NH₃ by

N loss through NH₃ volatilization in flooded rice. Pantnagar (U.P.), India.

Treatment ^a loss	N loss (%)							Cumulative (%) in 28 d
	0-4 d	4-8 d	8-12 d	12-16 d	16-20 d	20-24 d	24-28 d	
Urea	4.2	4.4	4.7	2.9	0.9	0.8	0.6	18
USG deep placed	0.4	1.5	2.6	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.6	8
Linseed oil-coated urea	1.3	1.4	1.5	3.0	2.6	1.5	0.8	12
Neem oil-coated urea	1.3	1.4	1.7	2.9	2.6	1.5	0.8	12
Urea+p-benzoquinone	0.5	1.0	1.3	1.6	1.8	1.0	0.7	8
Urea + catechol	0.6	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.9	1.2	0.8	9
Urea + <i>Acacia arabica</i>	4.9	6.6	7.7	5.0	3.0	1.4	0.8	29
Urea + <i>Acacia catechol</i>	4.3	4.6	5.2	4.1	2.3	1.1	0.8	21
Urea + <i>Terminalia chebula</i>	4.4	5.7	6.2	4.8	3.0	1.1	0.8	26

^a Each treatment received 2.0 g urea.